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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“THE PLEA OF A YOUNGEST CHILD”

You were four decades and a three when I was born,
As the youngest fruit among your seven scions,
The day when I saw the wacky-quirky world,
Was the day when the King-Savior was born.

As I grew up from a parent of both educators,
Everybody's waiting if I'll meander your vocation,
Because embryonic mind still I am entangled,
To step on your footprints or to follow my passion.

Time hastily swift the years pass by,
My braggy-older siblings vaunt as their career rise,
Whereas, I am still rafting in my techy-picky race,
Engross to finish with my science of computer gage.

That uncertain night succumbs our father's life,
From laughter to tears wallow our hive,
As we mourn the sudden demise of our dad,
Our one big happy family no more but sad.

Little did I discern that they will all be ditching me,
Kissing good-bye to create their own family,
Leaving miles away to dig a greater opportunity,
And now I'm alone, only with mother at home.

Yearning one day that my older siblings return home,
Fly back to their nest no matter how far they go,
Waiting to hear again the buzzing sound like bees,
And shout the family's yell, one big happy family!

